

at 15 days after transplanting (DT) in an experiment on pest control using the variety ADT 31. Infestation data were taken at 30 DT.

For the stem borer, carbofuran at 0.5 kg a.i./ha effectively reduced deadhearts; increased doses of granules provided no better stem borer control (see table). **W**

Control of stem borer with carbofuran. Aduthurai, India.

Carbofuran 3% G (kg a.i./ha)	Deadhearts/10.8 sq m No.	Transformed value
0.0	83	8.3
0.5	13	3.3
1.0	7	2.5
2.0	6	2.2
C.D. (P = 0.05)		2.5

Effectiveness of root-soaking in insecticides for pest control in paddy

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Four insecticides—chlorpyrifos, cartap, carbofuran, and lindane—were compared

Effectiveness of insecticides and root-soaking durations against deadheart damage caused by stem borers. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Deadhearts/unit	
	No.	Transformed value
<i>Insecticides</i>		
Chlorpyrifos	11.8	3.9
Cartap	18.6	4.6
Carbofuran	35.8	6.5
Lindane	30.0	5.9
C.D. (P = 0.05)		1.9
<i>Duration of soaking</i>		
With gelatin		
20 min	48.2	6.2
40 min	24.9	4.1
60 min	28.2	5.0
Without gelatin		
20 min	26.5	4.9
40 min	28.0	4.9
60 min	15.4	3.8
Untreated control	53.8	6.9
C.D. (P = 0.05)		1.5

as root-soak treatments at 0.04% concentration with the variety ADT 31 during the 1977 kuruvai (June–Sept). Urea at 1% was digested in the treatment solutions. Gelatin at 6% in treatment solution was compared with no gelatin for root-soaking durations of 20,40, and 60 minutes.

Observations were made at 15 and 30 days after transplanting (DT) for whorl maggot, at 25 DT for jassids, and at 30 DT for stem borer. The treatments did not differ significantly in control of whorl maggot or jassids.

The differences in stem borer control among the four insecticides were statistically significant. Chlorpyrifos and cartap were equally superior to carbofuran and lindane for stem borer control (see table).

Soaking for 20,40, and 60 minutes with and without gelatin produced about equally significant effects. All treatments, except 1 soaking for 20 minutes in gelatin solution, were better than the control. There was no advantage in using gelatin. **W**

Soil and crop management

Paddy straw mat as a nursery bed cover for summer paddy crops

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Only a single kharif crop of paddy is now grown in the Punjab, but short-duration rice varieties may make a second summer crop of paddy possible. Such a summer crop would have to be transplanted in the second half of April, after the wheat harvest, and nurseries would have to be

sown in February or early March, when the soil temperature is low. This study was undertaken to develop practical technology for raising the soil temperature to improve seed germination and nursery growth.

Conservation of solar heat was compared in four treatments in flat beds (5 × 2 m) and raised beds (8 × 1.5 m) sown on 15 February 1977. In one treatment, the nursery bed was covered with polythene sheet immediately after sowing. The sheet was removed after

A healthy flat bed nursery for summer paddy crops. Punjab Agricultural University, India.

Effect of different covering materials on germination period, germination count, and soil temperature, Punjab Agricultural University, India.

	Treatments				Control
	Polythene	Paddy	Farmyard manure	Mean	
<i>Time to germination (days)</i>					
Flat bed	6	7	11	8	12
Raised bed	6	6	9	7	–
Mean	6	7	10	–	12
<i>Stand count at 15 days after sowing (no./100 sq cm)</i>					
Flat bed	35	54	10	33	9
Raised bed	50	44	23	39	–
Mean	43	49	17	–	9
<i>Mean soil temperature (°C)</i>					
Flat bed					
morning	15	16	11	14	10
evening	27	24	22	24	21
Raised bed					
morning	15	17	12	15	–
evening	28	24	20	24	–

complete seed germination. In another treatment, the nursery bed was covered with manually prepared paddy straw mat, 3 or 4 cm thick, every day before sunset. The bed was uncovered and exposed to the sun during the day. In the third treatment, a layer of farmyard manure, about 0.5 cm thick, was spread on the

bed immediately after sowing. The fourth treatment was an uncovered check plot.

Regardless of covering material, seed in the raised beds germinated earlier than those in the flat beds. Symptoms of iron chlorosis appeared in the raised beds at about 7 days after emergence and affected seedlings began to die at about

15 days. Seedlings in the flat beds remained healthy (see photo).

The type of cover affected the germination period and the number of seedlings per 100 sq cm. In the treatments covered with polythene and straw mat, seed began to emerge at 6 and 7 days after sowing, respectively. In the farmyard manure and control treatments, seedling emergence began 10 and 12 days after sowing (see table). The number of seedlings per 100 sq cm was 43 in the polythene treatment, 49 in the paddy straw mat, 17 in the farmyard manure cover, and 9 in the control. The paddy straw mat, followed by polythene, maintained the highest minimum temperature. Polythene, followed closely by paddy straw, maintained the highest evening temperature. Temperatures were lower in the farmyard manure and the control treatments.

The use of polythene may not be practical because of its cost and the accessory material required to properly spread it. But paddy straw mat is readily available to farmers and may be used as a cover to improve germination and hasten nursery growth for summer paddy crops. **W**

Methods of N application and weed control in gogoranch rice culture

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A preliminary trial on methods of N application and weed control was conducted on rice grown under gogoranch culture in Indramayu, Indonesia, during the early 1975–76 wet season. Basal treatments of triple superphosphate and muriate of potash fertilizers at the rates of 45 kg P₂O₅/ha and 50 kg K₂O/ha were used for all plots. Total N used for all treatments was 90 kg/ha.

Root zone placement gave more efficient use of N fertilizer than surface placement (see table). But when weeds

were effectively controlled by two weeding, surface application of higher rates of N (80 kg/ha) at 15 days after emergence (DE) gave almost the same yield as root zone placement using 40 kg/ha at 15 DE. Perforan herbicide and one weeding were little better than the unweeded check. Grasses were generally the dominant weeds in the

gogoranch culture, followed by sedges. Broadleaved weeds were a minor problem. Surface application using the higher rate of N (80 kg urea/ha) at 15 DE with two weeding gave higher yields than root zone placement using 40 kg/ha and less intensive methods of weeding. **W**

Effects of different methods of N application and weeding on rice grown under gogoranch culture. Cropping Systems Research, Indramayu, Indonesia, 1975–76.

Method of N application ^a	Yield (t/ha) using different weeding methods ^b				Av.
	1	2	3	4	
Root zone placement ^c	4.8	2.5	2.7	2.5	3.1
Surface banded ^c	3.2	2.4	2.2	1.6	2.3
Surface banded ^d	4.6	1.9	1.9	1.5	2.5
Av.	4.2	2.3	2.2	1.8	

^aAt 15 days after emergence.

^bTreatment 1 = two hand weeding at 15 and 35 days after seeding (DS); 2 = one hand weeding at 15 DS; 3 = two kg of Perforan (a.i.) applied as preemergence herbicide; 4 = unweeded check.

^c40 kg N/ha plus 50 kg N/ha at panicle initiation.

^d80 kg N/ha plus 10 kg N/ha at panicle initiation.